

Monocrotophos was applied topically at 0.5 µl, using a Burkard microapplicator with calibrated microsyringe. Treated insects were transferred to rice panicles of plants enclosed in mylar cages. The test had 10 insects/treatment with 4 replications.

Cages were kept in the phytotron at 27-30 °C, 60-80% relative humidity, and 12 h illumination. Mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment. LD₅₀

values were computed using probit analysis.

The lowest LD₅₀ value (µg/g) was for adult females and the highest for the 4th instar (see table). Regardless of body weight, the adult was more sensitive than the 4th and 5th instar. Lower insecticide dosages will control adults; higher dosages may be needed to control nymphs. □

Susceptibility of brown planthopper (BPH) and green leafhopper (GLH) to insecticides under different temperatures

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When LD₅₀ values are compared between locations, prevailing temperature could cause inconsistent results. We subjected BPH and GLH to six different temperatures after topical insecticide application.

Serial dosages of 7 insecticides were prepared in acetone solution and 0.1 µl and applied on the thoracic tergites of anaesthetized BPH and 0.2 µl on those of GLH. Twenty treated adults were placed in a plastic tumbler, provided with 10 two-week-old seedlings for food,

and transferred in Koitotron cabinets set at constant temperatures of 18 °C to 33 °C with natural daylength. Insect mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment and LD₅₀ values were computed using probit analysis.

BPH and GLH were susceptible to most of the insecticides at higher temperatures and to the pyrethroids at lower temperatures (see table). For BPH, all insecticides except cypermethrin and deltamethrin had lower LD₅₀ values at 33 °C than at 18 °C (see table). For GLH, all insecticides except carbaryl and the two pyrethroids were more potent at higher temperatures. Insecticide activity was comparable at the temperature range 27-30 °C. Temperatures before, during, and after treatment should be recorded to control their possible effect on insecticide activity. □

LD₅₀ values of BPH brachypterous adult females and GLH adult females at 6 temperatures. ^a IRRI phytotron, 1987.

Temp (°C)	LD ₅₀ (µg/g) in 24 h						
	BPMC	Carbaryl	Carbofuran	Cypermethrin	Deltamethrin	Diazinon	Malathion
<i>BPH</i>							
18	4.68 a	4.12 a	1.19 a	0.24 a	0.40 a	12.13 a	37.43 a
21	2.59 b	4.64 a	0.85 ab	0.25 a	0.53 a	8.36 a	23.95 a
24	1.92 b	3.91 a	0.74 abc	0.29 a	0.46 a	8.46 a	27.02 a
27	1.30 b	3.78 a	0.37 bc	0.33 a	0.57 a	6.76 a	14.38 a
30	1.70 b	4.08 a	0.39 bc	0.42 a	0.55 a	7.05 a	13.95 a
33	0.61 b	1.67 b	0.21 c	0.39 a	0.59 a	4.92 a	9.08 a
<i>GLH</i>							
18	6.85 a	4.38 a	3.42 a	0.14 b	0.12 b	36.20 a	11.83 a
21	7.00 a	5.38 a	2.88 ab	0.21 ab	0.27 b	27.61 b	12.05 a
24	4.40 ab	4.54 a	2.03 bc	0.14 b	0.54 ab	23.78 b	12.25 a
27	3.49 b	5.62 a	1.61 bc	0.25 ab	0.75 a	19.04 b	9.62 ab
30	2.30 b	3.70 a	1.68 bc	0.58 a	0.75 a	19.10 b	9.31 ab
33	1.66 b	4.41 a	1.17 c	0.57 a	0.71 a	19.36 b	6.99 b

^a Av of 3 replications, 20 insects/replication. In a column within a species, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Residues of quinalphos in rice

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We studied residues of quinalphos (0, 0-diethyl-D-[2-quinoxaly] phosphorothionate), widely used insecticide, in rice variety Lalat (ORS26-2014). The pesticide was sprayed at the recommended level (0.05%, or 0.25 kg ai/ha) and double the recommended level (0.1%, or 0.50 kg ai/ha). Plant samples were collected at 0, 10, 20, and 30 d after spraying and at harvest.

The spectrophotometric method was used to estimate residues of quinalphos, using p-nitrobenzyl pyridine as the chromogenic reagent. Recovery of quinalphos from fortified plant samples was 86-87%.

Mean initial residues of I 1.04 ppm (0.05%) and 18.86 ppm (0.1%) were reduced to 3.45 and 6.86 ppm 10 d after insecticide application, to 0.62 and 1.05 ppm 20 d after application, and to nondetectable levels 30 d after

Linear plot of first-order reaction of quinalphos in rice. Bhubaneswar, India.

application. Dissipation was 94.4% (0.05% and 0.1%) 20 d after application.

Rate of degradation with both applications seemed to follow the first-order reaction (see figure).

Fifty percent of the toxicant was reduced at 1.4 d and 1.95 d and the safe waiting period (T_{50}) was 15.9 d and 17.5 d for lower and higher applications.

Grain and straw samples had nondetectable levels of quinalphos. □

Effect of plant age on rice susceptibility to yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker)

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YSB, the most important of the 21 species of stem borers that attack rice, is widespread in tropical Asia and Japan. All rice crops, whether irrigated, lowland rainfed, upland, or deepwater, suffer damage. Adults oviposit on leaves and newly emerged larvae enter stems and feed on the inner walls, causing deadhearts at the vegetative stage and whiteheads at the reproductive stage.

We studied larval survival and degree of damage on rice plants of different ages. Seeding of IR64 was staggered so plants of different ages were available for simultaneous infestation with first-instar larvae. There were 12 pots/age group. Plants were thinned to 20 tillers/pot. Each pot was infested with 15 larvae hatched from field-collected egg masses and then covered with a 40 × 100-cm mylar film cage.

Four pots were dissected at 18 d and 4 pots at 25 d after infestation (DAI). Adults were allowed to emerge on four pots.

Larvae recovered by dissecting plants at 18 DAI were weighed individually. Individuals recovered from plants at 25 DAI could not be weighed as some had reached the prepupal stage. The remaining plants were cut about 20 cm above the soil for easy observation of emerging adults.

Survival and development of *S. incertulas* larvae and damage at different days after infestation (DAI) on IR64 plants of different ages.^a IRRRI, 1987.

Plant age (DAS)	Larval wt (mg/larva) 18 DAI	Survival (%)		Adults emerged (no.)	Deadhearts (%)	
		18 DAI	25 DAI		18 DAI	25 DAI
10	0 e	0 d	1 d	0 d	10 c	9 e
16	7.8 d	2 cd	2 cd	0 d	22 b	12 d
22	8.9 d	2 cd	4 cd	0 d	25 b	14 d
28	12.8 c	4 c	5 c	5 c	27 b	16 cd
34	34.1 ab	68 a	55 a	33 b	69 a	66 ab
40	41.2 a	68 a	52 a	63 a	69 a	11 a
46	33.3 ab	37 b	49 a	48 b	57 a	56 b
52	29.8 b	28 b	28 b	41 b	27 b	26 c

^aAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Fewer larvae survived and emerged on younger rice plants (see table). Survival increased with plant age up to 34 and 40 d after sowing (DAS), then declined progressively on plants aged 46 and 52 DAS. Fewer deadhearts were

observed in younger plants than in plants at 34, 40, and 46 DAS; deadheart count declined sharply at 52 DAS.

Larvae were heaviest on plants at 40 DAS; they weighed less on plants at 34, 46, and 52 DAS. □

Fecundity of several green leaf hopper (GLH) populations in Indonesia

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A greenhouse experiment Jan-Apr 1985 was designed to study the fecundity of GLH *Nephotettix virescens* Distant

populations from four sites in Indonesia: Salutete and Pangkajene (South Sulawesi), Tawamalewe (South East Sulawesi), and Citamiang (West Java).

A pair of mature GLH was placed in a test tube containing a 2-wk-old TNI seedling. Number of eggs laid was counted daily under the microscope. Fecundity differed in the four locations (see table). □

Fecundity of *N. virescens* Distant from four Indonesian populations^a, 1985.

Origin of population	Pre-oviposition period (d)	Oviposition period (d)	Postoviposition period (d)	Eggs (no.)
Salutete	6 a	23 a	2 a	260 a
Pangkajene	8 a	11 b	2 a	81 c
Tawamalewe	7 a	18 ab	2 a	151 bc
Citamiang	6 a	22 a	1 a	213 ab

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Effect of sweep-net sampling at rice crop reproductive stage on yield

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Orthopteran predators such as *Metioche vittaticollis*, *Anaxipha longipennis*, and

Conocephalus longipennis, as well as certain pests such as rice bugs and green leafhoppers often are abundant in fields where rice plants are at the reproductive stage. Sweep-net sampling, an efficient method of collecting these highly mobile insects in the field, might damage the flowering plants and affect yields. Yet it is important to sample insects to make